

Gender Inequality in Healthcare Seeking: A Cross-Sectional Study in Slums of Burdwan Municipality, West Bengal

Sayanti Chingri¹, Raston Mondal², Primit Goswami³, Soumik Dandapat⁴, Arif Hossain⁵, Aprajita Jha⁶, Suman Sannigrahi⁷, Haimanti Bhattacharya⁸

¹Intern, Burdwan Medical College Hospital, West Bengal

²Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Burdwan Medical College Hospital, West Bengal

³Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Burdwan Medical College Hospital, West Bengal

^{4,5,6,7,8}JR, Department of Community Medicine, Burdwan Medical College Hospital, West Bengal

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Primit Goswami

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Abstract:

Introduction: Gender profoundly shapes society. Socially constructed norms cause chaos, leading to inequality. Women in low and middle-income countries lack access to resources like employment, education, and healthcare compared to men, affecting their status and lifespan. This study addresses this inequality.

Aim and Objectives: The study aimed to assess gender inequality and its correlates in healthcare seeking, by associations, if any, between gender and healthcare utilization, gender prioritization, household decision-making power, and sociodemographic factors in Burdwan, West Bengal.

Methods: This study was a descriptive cross-sectional study conducted in 7 randomly selected slums of Burdwan Municipality, WB. The study included calculated subjects of 252 adults, with 36 households (18 males & 18 females) randomly selected from each slum. Interviews were conducted to assess socio-demographic characteristics, healthcare access and utilization, household member prioritization for medical treatment, healthcare, and economic decision-making power. Descriptive statistics and chi-square tests were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics 23.0.

Results: Women reported higher underutilization of healthcare than men (13.5% vs. 8.7%) and were more likely to prioritize men, especially sons, for medical treatment (68.3%). In contrast, men showed equitable prioritization (49.2% prioritized men). Women were less likely to be the primary healthcare decision-makers for themselves than men (42.9% vs. 55.6%) but men were reported as primary decision-makers for children's health and healthcare payments.

Conclusion: This study reveals how societal norms and attitudes marginalize women and favour men's health, leading to significant gender disparities in health among Burdwan's slum dwellers. Women's reduced access to care results from both internal and external gender discrimination.

Keywords: Decision-making, Gender, Healthcare-seeking, Slum.

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Introduction

The role of gender is very vital in shaping a society. Behaviour has an important role in health disparities- for example, young men take greater risks, causing injury and violent death, and men smoke more [1]. Gender and health are related [2-4], as socially constructed gender norms create inequality [5]. This is seen while contrasting men's and women's propensity for seeking health. It has been demonstrated that disparities in the health-seeking behaviours of men and women are influenced by a variety of complex factors, including gender relations, gendered conceptions of health, cultural beliefs about how male and female

bodies differ, and gendered disparities in access to healthcare [6]. Studies conducted worldwide also demonstrate that the relationship between gender and health-seeking behavior varies depending on the setting [7], including slum areas [8]. Additionally, these studies imply that variables such as culturally-prescribed gender roles [9], power relations [10], structural positions and age hierarchies [11], or economic factors apart from cultural context [12] also impact gender variations in health-seeking behavior. Women most frequently give birth at home as a result of financial hardships and resistance from spouses or family members to giving birth in a

hospital. In situations like this, the husband or the elder members of his family usually decide whether to seek medical attention [13,14]. World bank revealed that global gender inequality has increased over the decades in world as well as in India. With seeds of inequality in our society, restrictive gender values and expectations led to unequal access to healthcare facilities, affecting an individual's lifespan [15]. Early marriage and pregnancy [16], sexual violence [17], anaemia [18] and poor educational opportunities all contribute to ill health among female adolescents in India including whole south-east Asia.

The share of participation of women in almost every field is unequal compared to males [19]. Moradhvaj (2019) believed that the involvement of women in non-economic activities is the primary reason to alienate them from access to better healthcare facilities [20].

The disparity is also evident in the rates of hospital admissions. The gender ratio of overnight hospital stays and emergency medical admissions for high-income countries are almost similar [21]. But in the low and middle-income countries, the male-female ratio stood at 1.4 for general admissions (barring obstetric care) and 2.2 for emergency abdominal surgeries [22]. Studies have shown that both sexes have equal probabilities of getting affected by diseases. But due to specific gender roles, orthodox mentality, and socially constructed beliefs, there lies inequality in health [23].

In this above context, this study will generate evidence regarding appropriateness of healthcare seeking by adults of both genders residing in a slum setting. The presence of these problems their estimated magnitude, especially in a marginalised population will help the healthcare delivery system of this locality to better understand gender inequality and plan for better access to healthcare by all the residents.

Objectives:

The study aims to estimate differences in healthcare prioritization and utilization among household members, compare healthcare and economic decision-making power, and explore the relationship between the gender gap and socio-demographic characteristics among adults aged 18-59 years residing in the slums of Burdwan Municipality, West Bengal.

Materials and Methods:

The study is a descriptive type of observational study with a cross-sectional design that was conducted in the slums of Burdwan Municipality, Purba Bardhaman District, and West Bengal from 1st to 31st August 2022.

Ethical approval was duly obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee of Burdwan Medical College and approval and permissions were also obtained from the Head of the Institution, BMCH before conducting the study.

Study population

All adult men and women aged 18-59 years and residing in the slums of Burdwan municipality for at least one year before the day of data collection were included in the study. Those who were unwilling to give consent or were absent from their house in spite of two consecutive visits were excluded from the study.

Sample size

A sample size of 252 adults (126 men and 126 women) was calculated using the formula

$$n = \frac{z_{1-\alpha/2}^2 [P_1(1-P_1) + P_2(1-P_2)]}{d^2}$$

taking the prevalence P1, P2 from a study done by Azad AD, Charles AG et al in the gender gap and healthcare: associations between gender roles and factors affecting healthcare access in Central Malawi, that reported women were less likely than men to secure community-sourced healthcare financial aid (68.6% vs. 88.8%)[24] with 95% confidence interval and with an absolute precision of 0.1 including a dropout rate of 5%.

Sampling methods

Study subjects were selected by multistage random sampling, wherein the first stage, 7 slums (5% of total 144 registered slums under Burdwan Municipality) were chosen randomly. In the second stage, from sampling frame of all enlisted adults of those pre-selected slums, 36 subjects (i.e., 18 males and 18 females) were selected by SRS in each slum and were interviewed.

Study tools and techniques

Selected subjects were interviewed by going to their residences. The data was collected with a pre-designed, pre-tested schedule containing questions from questionnaires used to assess socio-demographic characteristics, access to utilisation of healthcare, prioritization of household members for medical treatment, healthcare and economic decision-making power. Prior to data collection, the informed consent of study participants was taken with the assurance that the confidentiality of the given information will be maintained.

Data analysis

The data were analysed by using various statistical software, following which they were organized and presented by applying the principles of descriptive

statistics and chi-square test was used as applicable, to determine if there is a significant relationship between gender and other categorical variables.

Observation and Results

Sociodemographic Characteristics of the study participants: Within 7 slums, 252 adults i.e., 126(50%) men & 126(50%) women were surveyed taking 36 adults from each of the slums. The mean age of the study population was found to be 39 years with the majority of the population lying in the age group range of 18-40 years. All the study participants were Hindu by religion. Overall, participants reported their average monthly income as 9000 INR (110.24 US\$) supporting 5 households including 1 child. The majority of the study population were Scheduled Caste (37.3%), married (78.6%), unemployed (40.9%), illiterate (43.3%), and belonged to

upper middle socio-economic status (45.2%) (Modified B.G. Prasad scale). There was a significant relationship between gender and caste (p value=0.011), marital status (p value=0.001), employment status (p value=0.000), and spouse employment status (p value=0.000).

Whereas no significant differences were found between gender and educational level and socioeconomic status. Women were more likely to be married (p value=0.001), less likely to be employed (p value=0.000), and more likely to be in the unreserved category (p value= 0.011) than men. Spouse employment status being significantly related to gender revealed women reported a higher number of employed spouses (Employed, Men:30.9 vs. Women:70.0) than men. (Table 1).

Table 1: Distribution of study participants according to their sociodemographic characteristics by gender (n=252)

Variables	Men n (%) (N=126)	Women n (%) (N=126)	Total n (%) (N=252)
Age			
18-30	37(38.1)	27(27.0)	64(32.5)
31-40	32(33.0)	31(31.0)	63(32.0)
41-50	20(20.6)	21(21.0)	41(20.8)
51-59	8(8.2)	21(21.0)	29(14.7)
Age (year) Mean (SD)	39.21(16.64)	42.07(19.34)	36.35(12.79)
Caste, n (%)			
SC	50(39.7)	44(34.9)	94(37.3)
ST	8(6.3)	22(17.5)	30(11.9)
OBC	24(19.0)	12(9.5)	36(14.3)
UR	44(34.9)	48(38.1)	92(36.5)
Family Type			
Nuclear	61(48.4)	63(50.0)	124(49.2)
Joint	65(51.6)	63(50.0)	128(50.8)
Marital Status,			
Never Married	22(17.5)	5(4)	27(10.7)
Currently Married	96(76.2)	102(81.0)	198(78.6)
Divorced Or separated	3(2.4)	2(1.6)	5(2)
Widow Or Widower	5(4.0)	17(13.5)	22(8.7)
Employment Status			
Self Employed	31(24.6)	23(18.3)	54(21.4)
Employed	71(56.3)	22(17.5)	93(36.9)
Unemployed	22(17.5)	81(64.3)	103(40.9)
Retired	2(1.6)	0(0.0)	2(0.8)
Educational Level			
Illiterate	51(40.5)	58(46.0)	109(43.3)
Primary School Certificate (1-4)	14(11.1)	14(23.0)	28(11.1)
Middle School Certificate (5-8)	35(27.8)	29(23.0)	64(25.4)
High School Certificate (9-10)	13(10.3)	16(12.7)	29(11.5)
Intermediate or Diploma (11-12)	13(10.3)	9(7.1)	22(8.7)
Socio-Economic Status (Modified B.G. Prasad Scale)			
Upper (\geq 7863)	61(48.4)	49(38.9)	110(43.7)
Upper Middle (3931-7862)	54(42.9)	60(47.6)	114(45.2)
Middle (2359-3930)	9(7.1)	14(11.1)	23(9.1)
Lower Middle (1179-2358)	2(1.6)	1(0.8)	3(1.2)

Lower (<1179)	0(0.0)	2(1.6)	2(0.8)
Spouse Age			
18-30	37(38.1)	27(27.0)	64(32.5)
31-40	32(33.0)	31(31.0)	63(32.0)
41-50	20(20.6)	21(21.0)	41(20.8)
51-59	8(8.2)	21(21.0)	29(14.7)
Spouse age, (Years) Mean (SD)	38.31(11.89)	35.53(10.27)	41.01(12.75)
Spouse Employment Status			
Self Employed	11(11.3)	18(18.0)	29(14.7)
Employed	30(30.9)	70(70.0)	100(50.8)
Unemployed	56(57.7)	12(12.0)	68(34.5)
Spouse Educational Level, n (%)			
Illiterate	48(49.5)	40(40.0)	88(44.7)
Primary School Certificate (1-4)	10(10.3)	18(18.0)	28(14.2)
Middle School Certificate (5-8)	20(20.6)	20(20.0)	40(20.3)
High School Certificate (9-10)	14(14.4)	14(14.0)	28(14.2)
Intermediate or Diploma (11-12)	5(5.2)	8(8.0)	13(6.2)
Average Monthly Income, (Rupees) Mean (SD)	9129.37(7668.49)	9244.84(7399.27)	9013.89(7956.49)
Spouse income, (Rupees) Mean (SD)	3749.69(4341.96)	1408.65(2119.07)	6020.50(4731.98)

Access to and utilization of healthcare: Among the entire study population, 89.7% reported that they could secure additional funds (financial support) for healthcare from their family members or the community.

Women reported a higher ability to secure additional funds in conditions they're unable to afford (91.3% in women vs. 88.1% in men). Additional funds referred to the surplus cost of acquiring healthcare which is not included in the free services offered by the healthcare system.

Amongst the whole population, 11.1% population reported being seriously ill in the past and did not seek healthcare. Underutilization of healthcare was more likely to be reported by women than by men (13.5% vs. 8.7%) (Table 2)

Prioritization of household members for medical treatment: The most common choice for prioritization of household members for medical treatment

was a man (58.7%) and to be more specific, a son (27%).

Women were more likely to prioritize men for medical treatment (68.3%), although men were equitable regarding prioritization (49.2% prioritized men, p value= 0.002) as depicted in Figure 1(a). Overall report showed women prioritized their husbands (32.5%) and sons (31%) over themselves (17.5) and their daughters (11.1); whereas men reported prioritizing their sons (23%) and wives (19.8%) over themselves (15.9%) and their daughters (13.5%). (p value = 0.001) Figure 2(a).

Significant prioritization of other household females and other household males for medical treatment was reported by men (27.8%, p value= 0.001) Figure 2(a). 'Other female' members included mother and sister, and, 'other male' members included father and brother.

Figure 1: Bar diagram showing prioritization of household members for medical treatment by Gender Prioritization

Figure 2: Bar diagram showing prioritization of household members for medical treatment by household members. ($p=0.001$, $\chi^2=20.775$)

Decision making power in households: Women were less likely to be reported as the primary healthcare decision maker for themselves than men (42.9% vs. 55.6%, p value=0.000).

Similar report was found when asked about the primary healthcare decision maker for children’s health that indicated men were more likely to take decision regarding children’s healthcare too. (44.3%, p value= 0.03). Nearly three out of four (73.8%) participants reported that men were the financial decision maker for healthcare payments. Only a quarter of women (25%) reported making healthcare

payment decision themselves over men (73.8%, p value=0.001) (Fig.3) Decision regarding minor household purchases that included food & clothing were respectively taken by both the genders (Men: 44.4%, Women: 49.2%, p value= 0.736). The primary decision maker for large household purchases as reported by majority of the population was a man (58.7%, p value=0.545). The large household purchases included land, electrical gadgets, vehicles etc. Both men and women reported that the capital earned by them was equally controlled by the respective genders. (Men: 45.2%, Women: 49.2%, p value= 0.799). (Table-2)

Table 2: Distribution of study participants according to their decision-making power by gender (n= 252)

	Family member deciding about	Decision makers	Response of Male n (%)	Response of Female n (%)	Total n (%)	χ^2 , Df, P-Value
Healthcare Decision Making Power	Own health care	Male	92(73.0)	48(38.1)	140(55.6)	31.1162, 2, <0.001
		Female	33(26.2)	75(59.5)	108(42.9)	
		Both	1(0.8)	3(2.4)	4(1.6)	
	Children's healthcare	Male	54(53.5)	39(35.8)	93(44.3)	6.790, 2, 0.03
		Female	32(31.7)	50(45.9)	82(39.0)	
		Both	15(14.9)	20(18.3)	35(16.7)	
	Paying for healthcare	Male	105(83.3)	81(64.3)	186(73.8)	13.351, 2, 0.001
		Female	19(15.1)	44(34.9)	63(25)	
		Both	2(1.6)	1(0.8)	3(1.2)	
Economic Decision-Making Power	Major household purchases	Male	73(57.9)	75(59.5)	148(58.7)	1.214, 2, 0.545
		Female	44(34.9)	46(36.5)	90(35.7)	
		Both	9(7.1)	5(4.0)	14(5.6)	
	Minor household purchases	Male	53(42.1)	59(46.8)	112(44.4)	0.612, 2, 0.736
		Female	65(51.6)	59(46.8)	124(49.2)	
		Both	8(6.3)	8(6.3)	16(6.3)	
	How to spend the earned money	Male	58(46.0)	56(44.4)	114(45.2)	0.0450, 2, 0.799
		Female	60(47.6)	64(50.8)	124(49.2)	
		Both	8(6.3)	6(4.8)	14(5.6)	

Male includes husband, brother, father, son etc and female includes wife, sister, mother, daughter etc. From table 2, we could interpret that healthcare decision making power of the study participants is significantly related to gender; whereas economic decision-making power is not significantly related to gender.

Discussion

In the present study, the majority of the population were in the age group 18-40 years with an average of 36.35(\pm 12.79) years and all followed Hinduism, whereas a study conducted in Central Malawi [24], the average age of the respondent was 41.7 (\pm 12.1) years with more than half of the population (58.5%) being protestant and nearly one-fourth were Roman Catholics.

In our study, the majority (78.6%) were currently married followed by never married or single (10.7%), widow or widower (8.7%), and divorced or separated (2%). Whereas in a study done regarding gender inequity in rural Nigerians, the majority (~91.0%) were currently married or living with a partner and <10.0% were not currently married.

In our study, gender was significantly related to employment status with majority being unemployed (40.9%) among which unemployment was largely observed in women (64.3%) than men (17.5%). Nearly 56.3% men were employed and 24.6% were self-employed as compared to women who were less likely to be employed (17.5%) and self-employed (18.3%). In a study among the Malawian population [24], majority were self-employed (89.2%) that included 84.8% women and 93.1% men. IN both the

studies, men were more likely to be self-employed than women.

In our study, majority (43.3%) of study subjects were illiterate, followed by 25.4% who received education till middle school (Class V to VIII), 11.5% till high school (Class IX & X), 11.1% till primary school (Class I-IV) and 8.7% till intermediate or diploma level (Class XI, XII and above). Whereas maximum population (61.5%) in a study regarding gender gap and healthcare in Central Malawi[24] was educated up to primary school followed by secondary school (26.0), no education (11.0%) and higher education (1.5%).

In our study, majority of study subjects belonged to Upper middle SES (45.2%) and Upper SES (43.7%) on the basis of B.G. Prasad scale, only 9.1% belonged to middle class, 1.2% to lower middle SES and 0.8% belonged to lower SES (B.G. Prasad scale).

In the present study, the majority of the spouse belonged to 18-40 years with an average age of 41.01(\pm 12.75) years which is similar to the study in Central Malawi[24] where the average spouse age was 41.3 (\pm 12.4) years. In our study, majority of spouse were illiterate (44.7%) as compared to the study in Central Malawi[24] where majority of the spouse had education till Primary school (69.3)%. Majority of spouse (50.8%) were employed followed by unemployed (34.5%) and self-employed (14.7%) in our study in contrast to a study in—where maximum was self-employed. (89.2%).

The average number of households and children in our study were nearly 5 and 1 respectively as

compared to 6 and 4 in the study in Central Malawi[24].

In our study, 89.7% of the entire study population reported that they could secure additional funds (financial support) for healthcare from their family members or the community. Women also reported higher ability to secure additional funds in conditions they're unable to afford. Underutilization of healthcare was more likely to be reported by women than that of men (13.5% vs. 8.7%, p value=0.229). Similar reports were observed in a study on the gender gap and healthcare in Central Malawi[24], where 78.5% population reported to secure financial support for healthcare. In contrast to our study, Malawian women significantly reported a lower ability for securing additional funds than men (68.6% vs 88.8%, $p < 0.001$). Underutilization of healthcare was significantly more in women than men (37.2% vs. 22.4%, $p = 0.02$).

The most common choice for prioritization of household members for medical treatment was a man (58.7%) and to be more specific, a son (27%) in our study. This neglect of girls was also observed previously in the literature[26] where women reported prioritizing to feed their sons before other members of the family in times of scarcity.

Our study revealed women prioritizing their husbands (32.5%) and sons (31%) over themselves (17.5%) and their daughters (11.1%) and men reported prioritizing their sons (23%) and wives (19.8%) over themselves (15.9%) and their daughters (13.5%) (p value = 0.001) which is similar to a study conducted regarding the gender gap and healthcare where women prioritized their sons (38.2%) and husbands (28.4%) rather than themselves (18.6%) and their daughters (12.7%) and men prioritized their daughters (36.7%) and themselves (30.6%) above their sons (15.3%) and wives (12.2%) ($p < 0.001$).

In the current study, women were less likely to be reported as the primary healthcare decision maker for themselves (p value=0.000) as well as for their children's healthcare (p value= 0.03) than men. Similar results were found in a study in Central Malawi that revealed women not being the primary healthcare decision maker for themselves ($p=0.003$). In a study regarding gender inequity in terms of barriers to women's access to skilled pregnancy care in Nigeria pointed out men being the final decision maker regarding women's access to skilled pregnancy. This was majorly due to the financial dependence of women on their spouses or partners.

Our study as well as in the study at Malawi significantly revealed men to be the healthcare financial decision maker as compared to women and decisions regarding minor household purchases were respectively taken by both genders equally. It was found in both studies that decisions regarding large

household purchases were majorly taken by men than women and nearly both genders equally made decisions regarding the expenditure of the earned capital.

Limitation

The findings of this study should be interpreted with caution due to its limited generalizability, as the research was confined to just seven slums within the field practice area of Burdwan Medical College. Additionally, a key limitation of the study was the reliance on self-reported data. Respondents may have provided answers that they believed to be socially acceptable, potentially leading to an underestimation of the true extent of gender inequalities.

Conclusion

The current study underscores the profound impact of societal norms and individual attitudes that marginalize women and disproportionately prioritize men's health, contributing to significant gender disparities in healthcare access. These entrenched societal beliefs often hinder women from prioritizing their own health and that of their daughters, leading to long-term adverse outcomes. To address this, the study advocates for targeted interventions aimed at boosting women's self-esteem, encouraging them to prioritize their health, and fostering a culture where their health concerns are taken seriously.

Such interventions are crucial in empowering women to confidently seek healthcare for themselves and their daughters, thereby narrowing the healthcare access gap that disproportionately affects them. Additionally, future research should focus on integrating gender norms into intervention planning and execution, aiming to raise public awareness about these norms. This approach will empower women to advocate for their health and that of other women and girls, fostering a more equitable healthcare system.

Implications

The study aims to provide valuable insights into the healthcare-seeking behaviors of adults of both genders living in a slum setting. It may uncover significant challenges related to health-related and economic decision-making power within the study population, contributing to inadequate healthcare-seeking practices. By identifying these issues and estimating their magnitude, particularly within this marginalized community, the findings will enable the local healthcare delivery system to better understand gender inequality and develop strategies to improve healthcare access for all residents.

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